

An Autopsy Based Study of Socio-Etiological Aspects of Unnatural Deaths in Reproductive Age Group FemalesSanjeet Kumar¹, Sawan Mundri², Anand Kumar³, Sanjay Kumar⁴, Kumar Shubhendu⁵¹Senior Resident, Department of FMT, SNMMC, Dhanbad, Jharkhand²Assistant Professor, Department of FMT, RIMS, Ranchi, Jharkhand³Senior Resident, Department of FMT, RIMS, Ranchi, Jharkhand⁴Associate Professor and HOD, Department of FMT, RIMS, Ranchi, Jharkhand⁵Assistant Professor, Department of FMT, RIMS, Ranchi, Jharkhand

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Education is a basic entitlement for each female in India according to the Right to Education Act of 2009, duly highlighted by the Indian government in its "Beti Bachao Beti Padhao" initiative, which effectively combines efforts to prevent female feticide with promoting girls' education. Educating girls positively impacts the socio-economic and health standards and reduces inequality in society. Socioeconomic status encompasses not just income but also educational attainment and financial security, as well as subjective perceptions of social status and social class. Apropos of betterment in the status of women in India; evils of illiteracy, ignorance and dowry, economic slavery, crimes like homicide, sexual assault would have to be completely eradicated to ensure their rightful place in society.

Material and Methods: The current study was conducted in the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, Jharkhand from April 2021 to March 2022 (i.e., 12 months). Total autopsies conducted during this period was 3840. Among these, 225 instances pertained to females within the reproductive age bracket in accordance with the predetermined selection criteria of the study.

Result: The highest proportion of women were educated up to high school (29.33%), with 20% educated up to middle school. A mere 1.33% held a professional degree, while 17.78% reported as being illiterate. Maximum number of cases were housewives, students, and laborers by profession. A significant portion of cases belonged to socioeconomic class II. Accidental death was the most prevalent, followed by suicidal incidents, with burn being the leading cause of death followed by road traffic accidents across all educational, occupational, and socioeconomic strata.

Conclusion: Deaths in women of reproductive age that are deemed unnatural accounted for 5.86% of the total cases examined during the study duration. Consequently, this necessitates careful consideration and the implementation of additional preventive and corrective interventions, particularly given that such deaths disproportionately affect women with lower levels of education and those who are unemployed. Moreover, it is crucial to note that these deaths are avoidable.

Keyword- Homicide, sexual assault, reproductive age of female, unnatural death

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Introduction

In the Indian societal context, women occupy a subordinate position across various domains including family, religion, law, and media. Aspects like reproduction, workforce participation, sexuality, and control over means of production are regulated by cultural norms. Consequently, women tend to lag behind men in social standing in these spheres. A stark reality concerning women's education in India is the prevalent parental inclination towards investing in sons' education over daughters'. This preference stems from the common belief that sons will provide care in old age, while daughters are expected to marry and join another family.

The assessment of the status of girls and women within society, along with the manner in which they are regarded, plays a fundamental role in the advancement of society. There is a notable shift occurring within society with regards to the recognition of women as professionals, contributors to household income, autonomous thinkers, caregivers within families, and as individuals bearing the responsibility of childbirth. Women have demonstrated their capability to perform on par with men in numerous fields, showcasing their proficiency and, in some instances, even surpassing their male counterparts.

Fewer women are now residing in their homes in India. There has been a slight enhancement in female labour force participation rates recently. [1] The involvement of female entrepreneurs is critical in the Indian economy, exerting a notable impact by creating job opportunities, expediting progress, and promoting prosperity. Women represent 14% (approximately 8 million) of all entrepreneurs in India. Nevertheless, the economic input of Indian women remains below half of the global average. If a greater number of women could enter the workforce, India has the potential to increase its annual growth by several percentage points. [2]

Education is viewed as the paramount instrument for empowering women within society. It serves to foster the growth of an individual's character, while simultaneously contributing significantly to the realms of economic, social, and cultural progress. The education of women is instrumental in driving substantial advancements in societal dynamics. Key social advantages stemming from this include a reduction in fertility rates, diminished infant mortality rates, and decreased maternal mortality rates.

The overall human functioning is influenced by the socio-economic status, encompassing both physical and mental health. Factors like decreased educational attainment, poverty, and deteriorating health associated with low socio-economic status have a lasting impact on our societal structure.

The age group considered to be reproductive spans from 15 to 44 years [3] in India and serves as a crucial indicator for human development. Any disruption within this age group, particularly among females, can have implications on the well-being of the succeeding generation, as well as on socio-economic progress and the overall fabric of society. The prevalence of unnatural deaths [4] is notably elevated within this reproductive age bracket, often attributed to a range of socio-etiological factors. [5] The distribution of such deaths provides insight into the existing societal and regional social and mental health landscapes. The frequency of unnatural deaths among women is on the rise, paralleling the escalating rates of gender-based violence compared to general crime rates in the Indian context. [6]

Violence against women represents a significant public health issue. According to estimates from the World Bank, the combination of Rape and Domestic violence accounts for 5% of healthy years of life. This form of abuse often remains concealed, not disclosed to neighbours, relatives, clinicians, and researchers. Such non-disclosure can be attributed to the prevalent values, norms, and customs within various societies, as well as to individual feelings of shame, guilt, and fear of

retaliation. Furthermore, social taboos and societal customs associated with victimization contribute to the perpetuation of this issue.⁷ Across nearly 50 population-based surveys conducted worldwide, findings indicate that a significant percentage of women, ranging from 10% to over 50%, have reported experiencing physical violence, mistreatment, or harm from a male at some point in their lives.[8]

Materials and Methods

The research was carried out at the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi from April 2021 to March 2022. A total of 3840 post-mortem examinations were performed during this timeframe, with 225 involving women of reproductive age. Extensive data on factors such as educational background, socioeconomic status, cause and manner of death, among others, were gathered using structured questionnaires through comprehensive interviews with different parties and adherence to established autopsy procedures.

Aim: To study the socio-etiological aspects of unnatural deaths in reproductive age group females.

Objectives: To find out the relationship between pattern of unnatural deaths in women of reproductive age and their levels of education, employment, and socio-economic standing.

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Duration: One year

Inclusion Criteria:

Unnatural causes of death in women of reproductive age group.

Reliable history.

Exclusion Criteria:

Natural causes of death in women of reproductive age group.

Unidentified bodies.

Decomposed bodies.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered and template was generated in Microsoft Office Excel 2019. Preliminary codification of a subset of raw data was undertaken to facilitate meaningful interpretation. Subsequently, the data underwent analysis utilising SPSS version 20 designed for the Windows operating system. Following this, frequency tables and corresponding proportions were computed as part of the analytical process.

Modified B. G. Prasad socio-economic classification for May 2021[9] was used to delineate the socio-economic status of the deceased women.

Social class	Per capita income (₹) as per original classification in 1961	Per capita income (₹) as per modified classification in for May 2021
I	>100	>7863
II	50-99	3931-7862
III	30-49	2359-3930
IV	15-29	1179-2358
V	<15	<1179

Results

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to education of the deceased women

Education	No. of Cases	Percentage
Professional degree	3	1.33
Graduate	20	8.89
Intermediate / Diploma	24	10.67
High School	66	29.34
Middle School	45	20
Primary School	27	12
Illiterate	40	17.78
Total	225	100

The highest percentage of women had completed high school (29.33%), with 20% educated up to middle school, and 17.78% being illiterate.

Table 2: Distribution according to education of the deceased women and manner of death

Education	Manner of death									
	Accidental		Homicidal		Suicidal		Suspicious		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	n	%	n	%
Postgraduate	01	33.3	00	00	02	66.7	00	00	03	100
Graduate	08	40	00	00	11	55	01	05	20	100
Intermediate	12	50	01	4.2	09	37.5	02	8.3	24	100
High School	35	53	06	9.1	20	30.3	05	7.5	66	100
Middle School	34	75.6	03	6.7	07	15.6	01	2.2	45	100
Primary School	15	55.6	05	18.5	07	25.9	00	00	27	100
Illiterate	28	70	03	7.5	09	22.5	00	00	40	100
Total	133	59.1	18	08	65	28.9	09	04	225	100

Most common manner of death in women educated up to high school and middle school was accidental.

Table 3: Distribution according to education of the deceased and cause of death

Total	Cause of Death																	Total																				
	Illiterate		Primary		Middle		High		In-Graduate		Graduate		Postgradu-		Education		n	%																				
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	Burn	Drowning			Electrocution	Fall from height	Firearm	Hanging	Lightening	MD	Poisoning	RTA	Snakebite	Stab	Strangulation	Elephant Trample	Others							
65	10	09	19	17	05	05	00	00	00	05	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
28.9	25	33.3	42.2	25.8	20.8	20.8	00	00	25	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
10	04	01	02	01	02	02	01	02	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
4.4	10	3.7	4.4	1.5	8.3	8.3	1.5	8.3	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
03	00	00	00	03	00	00	03	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
1.3	00	00	00	4.5	00	00	4.5	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
06	01	02	02	01	00	00	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
2.7	2.5	7.4	4.4	1.5	00	00	1.5	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
04	01	00	00	03	00	00	03	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
1.8	2.5	00	00	4.5	00	00	4.5	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
34	04	02	04	10	07	06	10	07	06	06	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
15.1	10	7.4	8.9	15.2	29.2	30	15.2	29.2	30	30	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3	33.3
03	01	00	00	02	00	00	02	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
1.3	2.5	00	00	03	00	00	03	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
09	00	00	01	05	02	01	05	02	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
04	00	00	2.2	7.6	8.3	05	7.6	8.3	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05
18	00	03	00	10	02	02	10	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02
08	00	11.1	00	15.2	8.3	10	15.2	8.3	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
53	14	05	14	10	04	05	10	04	05	05	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
23.6	35	18.5	31.1	15.2	16.7	25	15.2	16.7	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	
07	02	00	02	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
3.1	05	00	4.4	1.5	4.2	05	1.5	4.2	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05
08	00	04	00	03	01	00	03	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
3.6	00	14.8	00	4.5	4.2	00	4.5	4.2	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
02	01	00	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00
0.9	2.5	00	2.2	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	
01	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	
0.4	2.5	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	
02	01	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	
0.9	2.5	3.7	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	
22.5	40	27	45	66	24	20	66	24	20	20	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03	
100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	

Most common cause of death in women educated up to high school and middle school was burn.

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to occupation of deceased women

Occupation	No. of Cases	Percentage
Business	02	0.9
Farmer	18	08
Housewife	93	41.4
Job	14	6.2
Laborer	37	16.4
Student	61	27.1
Total	225	100

Majority of the deceased women were housewives and students.

Table 5: Distribution according to occupation of deceased women and manner of death

Occupation	Manner of death									
	Accidental		Homicidal		Suicidal		Suspicious		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Business	01	50	01	50	00	00	00	00	02	100
Farmer	14	77.8	03	16.7	01	5.6	00	00	18	100
Housewife	57	61.3	08	8.6	23	24.7	05	5.4	93	100
Job	05	35.7	01	7.1	07	50	01	7.1	14	100
Laborer	26	70.3	03	8.1	08	21.6	00	00	37	100
Student	30	49.2	02	3.3	26	42.6	03	4.9	61	100
Total	133	59.1	18	08	65	28.9	09	04	225	100

Most common manner of death in housewives and students group was accidental.

Table 6: Distribution according to Occupation of deceased women and cause of death

Occupation	Cause of Death																																	
	Burn		Drowning		Electrocution		Fall from height		Firearm		Hanging		Lightening		MD		Poisoning		RTA		Snakebite		Stab		Strangulation		Elephant Trample		Others		Total			
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%				
Business	00		00		00		00		01		00		00		00		00		01		00		00		00		00		02		100			
Farmer	04		22.2		02		11.1		00		02		11.1		00		00		00		00		02		11.1		01		5.6		00		18	
Housewife	31		33.3		01		1.1		02		2.2		04		4.3		03		3.2		11		11.8		02		00		01		0.9		93	
Job	01		7.1		00		00		00		00		00		01		7.1		00		00		35.7		00		00		14		100			
Laborer	15		40.5		05		13.5		00		00		00		03		8.1		00		1		2.7		2.7		01		2.7		37		100	
Student	14		23		02		3.3		00		1.6		00		00		4.9		11		18		24.6		01		00		61		100			
Total	65		28.9		10		4.4		03		1.3		06		2.7		04		04		07		23.6		07		3.1		08		225		100	

Among housewives, students and laborers, accidents accounted for the maximum number of deaths followed by suicide, the most common cause of death being burn followed by road traffic accidents.

Table 7: Distribution according to socio economic status and manner of death

Socio-economic status	Manner of death									
	Accidental		Homicidal		Suicidal		Suspicious		Total	
	n	%	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
I	06	75	00	00	02	25	00	00	08	100
II	103	56.3	16	8.7	56	30.6	08	4.4	183	100
III	24	70.6	02	5.9	07	20.6	01	2.9	34	100
Total	133	59.1	18	08	65	28.9	09	04	225	100

The majority of cases belonged to socioeconomic class II, in which the most common manner of death was accidental followed by suicidal.

Table 8: Distribution according to socio-economic status and cause of death

Socio-economic Status	Cause of Death																															
	Burn		Drowning		Electrocution		Fall from height		Firearm		Hanging		Lightening		MD		Poisoning		RTA		Snakebite		Stab		Strangulation		Elephant Trample		Others		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
I	02	25	00	00	02	25	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	03	37.5	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00	00		
II	53	29	08	4.4	01	0.5	06	3.3	04	2.2	29	15.8	03	1.6	08	4.4	17	9.3	39	21.3	04	2.2	07	3.8	02	1.1	01	0.5	01	0.5		
III	10	29.4	02	5.9	00	00	00	00	00	00	04	11.8	00	00	01	2.9	01	2.9	11	32.4	03	8.8	01	2.9	00	00	00	00	00	00		
Total	65	28.9	10	4.4	03	1.3	06	2.7	04	1.8	34	15.1	03	1.3	09	04	18	08	53	23.6	07	3.1	08	3.6	02	0.9	01	0.4	02	0.9		

Burn was the most common cause of death in the majority of deceased women belonging to socio-economic class II, followed by road traffic accidents.

Discussion

Maximum number of women were educated up to high school (29.33%) followed by those who were educated up to middle school (20%). Only 1.33% women had some professional degree, with 17.78% being illiterate. Study by A K Srivastava [10] showed maximum incidence of unnatural deaths in victims who were educated till primary school (37%) followed by those who were illiterate. Study by Kailash U. Zine [11] also reported maximum cases (27% and 29%) in victims educated up to

primary and middle school respectively, with 12.5% victims being illiterate. Study by Hussain [12] showed maximum cases in the illiterate group. Similar findings were seen in study by Anitha et al [13] and Kulshrestha. [14]

Maximum number of cases were housewives (41.4%) followed by students (27.1%) and laborers (16.4%). Among these, accident accounted for maximum number of deaths in all occupational categories followed by suicide. In studies done by Anitha et al [13], Kailash [11] and Kulshrestha [14], maximum number of cases belonged to housewives followed by working and studying group of women. Among these, suicide accounted for maximum cases in all occupational categories followed by accidental.

Majority of cases belonged to grade II (81.33%) followed by grade III (15.11%) and grade I (3.55%) of socio-economic status. There were no cases belonging to grade IV and grade V. Among all grades, accident was the most common manner of death, with road traffic accidents accounting for maximum number of cases followed by accidental burn.

Contrary to this study, in the studies done by Anitha et.al [13] and Kulshrestha [14], maximum number of cases belonged to grade III followed by grade II and IV. There were no cases belonging to grade I and grade V. Among all grades, suicide was the most common manner of death, in which hanging accounted for the maximum number of cases.

Study done by Kailash [11] showed maximum cases belonged to grade IV followed by grade V, burns being the commonest cause of death in all grades and accounted for 34.4% cases in grade IV. Similar findings were observed in a study by Srivastava¹⁰ where 55% cases belonged to grade IV followed by grade III. Study done by Yusuf R Hussain¹² in Bangladesh showed the maximum incidence in grade IV followed by grade III.

Conclusion

In order to identify potential mitigating variables and look into the pattern of unnatural deaths among women in the reproductive age group, a study was carried out at the Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Ranchi from April 2021 to March 2022. In majority of cases, the deceased women were educated up to high school and middle school, with accidents being the most common manner of death and burns being the most common cause of death. Housewives, students, and laborers constituted the highest percentage of cases. Of these, accidents accounted for maximum number of deaths in all occupational categories followed by suicides, with the most common cause of death being burn followed by road traffic accidents. Majority of the deceased females belonged to grade II socioeconomic class, in whom also the pattern of deaths was similar.

Recommendations

The importance of literacy and vocational/professional courses for girls must be emphasized even more because, in spite of numerous government initiatives that have been in place for a very long time, illiteracy and literacy that is diminished by unemployability have a strong etiological link with unnatural deaths among women in the reproductive age group.

Girls should be encouraged to work in order to become economically independent. This should be complemented by safe environments at work and at home, as well as by challenging patriarchal beliefs. After all, a good socioeconomic status is not a

guarantee of complete physical, mental, or social well-being, even if the status comes from family advantages. Education and employment are indeed inversely proportional to different unresolved emotional anxieties that frequently precede suicidal thoughts.

Enforcing traffic laws strictly, holding recurring public awareness campaigns to stop domestic accidents, teaching women stress management techniques, and incorporating mental health services into primary care facilities are all vital steps that can help lower the number of untimely unnatural deaths among women in the reproductive age group.

Strengths and Limitations of the Study

Given the paucity of research, the current study adds to the body of knowledge regarding unnatural fatalities among women in the reproductive age group. To enable generalization of the results, more study with a greater number of participants and collaboration with the humanities is required to appositely comprehend various social variables.

Funding: None.

Ethical Committee Clearance: This Manuscript has been approved by Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) RIMS, Ranchi.

Acknowledgement: We are indebted to all the mortuary staffs.

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